

An asymptotic-preserving and exactly mass-conservative semi-implicit scheme for weakly compressible flows based on compatible finite elements

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Abstract

We present a novel asymptotic-preserving semi-implicit finite element method for weakly compressible and incompressible flows based on compatible finite element spaces. The momentum is sought in an $H(\text{div})$ -conforming space, ensuring exact pointwise mass conservation at the discrete level. We use an explicit discontinuous Galerkin-based discretization for the nonlinear convective terms, while treating the pressure and viscous terms implicitly, so that the CFL condition depends only on the fluid velocity. To handle shocks and damp spurious oscillations in the compressible regime, we incorporate an *a posteriori* limiter that employs artificial viscosity and is based on a discrete maximum principle. By using hybridization, the final algorithm requires solving only symmetric positive definite linear systems. As the Mach number approaches zero and the density remains constant, the method naturally converges to an $H(\text{div})$ -based discretization of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in the vorticity-velocity-pressure formulation. Several numerical tests validate the proposed method.

Keywords: finite element exterior calculus; compatible finite elements; semi-implicit scheme; weakly compressible isentropic flows; asymptotic preserving scheme; incompressible Navier-Stokes equations

1. Introduction

The numerical approximation of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations is an active topic of research in which compatible finite elements [1, 2, 3] have shown to be natural candidates for high order structure-preserving discretizations, that is, discretizations that conserve energy, the Hamiltonian structure of the original system, involutions, etc. Since the pioneering work of Cockburn, Kanschat and Schötzau [4], $H(\text{div})$ -based finite element approximations of the incompressible Euler equations [5, 6, 7] have become more and more attractive since they produce exactly divergence-free velocities. Extending these methods to the full Navier-Stokes equations is not a trivial task, since the viscous stress tensor is not bounded in $H(\text{div})$. There are two possible ways to circumvent this obstacle: the first is to use a DG based approximation of the viscous term as in [8, 9, 10], whereas the second is to introduce additional fields to obtain a conforming term [11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

On the other hand, the numerical approximation of compressible flows with compatible finite elements is still at the dawn. In particular, we mention the works by Gawlik and Gay-Balmaz [7, 16, 17], the Versatile Mixed Method by Miller and Williams [18] and the method for compressible magnetohydrodynamics by Carlier and Campos-Pinto [19]. These methods, however, struggle with nonsmooth solutions and shocks as they either employ nonconservative variables or lack nonlinear stabilization mechanisms.

In this paper, we present a novel asymptotic-preserving *semi-implicit* finite element method for time-dependent weakly compressible flows based on compatible finite element spaces. Our approach *deliberately*

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19 employs a *semi-implicit* time discretization. This means that the nonlinear convective terms are discretized
 20 *explicitly*, while all other terms are discretized *implicitly*. It is well-known from the literature [20, 21, 22,
 21 23, 24, 25] that the semi-implicit approach allows to avoid the dependence of the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy
 22 (CFL) stability condition on the sound speed, which is particularly useful for low Mach number flows, and
 23 at the same time it also allows to obtain a discretization that naturally results in symmetric positive definite
 24 (SPD) linear systems to be solved for the discrete pressure in each time step. In this paper, for the spatial
 25 discretization, we use compatible finite elements, i.e. we apply compatible finite element exterior calculus
 26 (FEEC): Raviart-Thomas elements are used for the momentum and discontinuous elements are employed
 27 for the density and for the entropy, ensuring pointwise conservation of mass. To handle shocks and prevent
 28 spurious oscillations, we incorporate an *a posteriori* artificial viscosity limiter based on the MOOD approach
 29 by Clain, Diot, and Loubère [26, 27, 28] and the ideas outlined in [29, 30].

30 Finally, our method makes use of the celebrated hybridization technique originally introduced by Arnold
 31 and Brezzi [31], which allows for a more efficient implementation.

32 The proposed scheme is asymptotic preserving (AP) in the low Mach number limit, i.e. when the Mach
 33 number approaches zero and the density is constant, we obtain a scheme for the incompressible Navier-Stokes
 34 equations which has many points in common with the MEEVC scheme by Palha and Gerritsma [11] and
 35 the HDG scheme by Lehrenfeld and Schöberl [8]. However, to the very best of our knowledge, the proposed
 36 methodology is completely new in the context of weakly compressible flows and this is also one of the first
 37 works that uses *a posteriori* limiting in the context of compatible finite element exterior calculus (FEEC).

38 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we recall the equations for weakly compressible
 39 flows, discussing a possible viscous regularization and their asymptotic limit when the Mach number
 40 approaches zero. In Section 3 we describe our numerical method. In Section 4 we validate the proposed
 41 scheme with several test cases.

42 2. Governing equations

We first consider the non-conservative density-momentum-entropy formulation of time-dependent inviscid
 weakly compressible isentropic flows

$$\partial_t \rho + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m} = 0, \quad (1a)$$

$$\partial_t \mathbf{m} + \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{m}) = 0, \quad (1b)$$

$$\partial_t S + \frac{\mathbf{m}}{\rho} \cdot \nabla S = 0. \quad (1c)$$

Here ρ , \mathbf{m} and S denote density, momentum and specific entropy, respectively. Although the equations
 can be formulated solely in these three variables, it is useful consider also the velocity $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{m}/\rho$ and the
 pressure $p = p(\rho, S)$, which is a function of the density and the entropy. With these additional variables,
 the momentum flux can be defined as

$$\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{m}} + \mathcal{F}_p = \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{m} + p \mathbf{I},$$

with \mathbf{I} being the identity tensor. The square of the isentropic speed of sound is defined as

$$c^2 \doteq \frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho}.$$

Equivalently, it is possible to consider the density as a function of pressure and entropy, i.e. $\rho = \rho(p, S)$.
 Then the inverse function theorem immediately gives

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} = \frac{1}{c^2}.$$

In this work we consider the ideal gas equation of state:

$$p(\rho, S) = \rho^\gamma e^{S/c_v}.$$

43 Here c_v is the specific heat at constant volume and γ is the ratio of specific heats. If not stated otherwise,
 44 we choose $c_v = 2.5$ and $\gamma = 1.4$.

45 *2.1. Viscous regularization*

In this work we consider the following viscous regularization of (1):

$$\partial_t \rho + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m} - \nabla \cdot (\epsilon_\rho \nabla \rho) = 0, \quad (2a)$$

$$\partial_t \mathbf{m} + \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{m}) - \nabla \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m} + \nabla \times \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \times \mathbf{m} = 0, \quad (2b)$$

$$\partial_t S + \frac{\mathbf{m}}{\rho} \cdot \nabla S - \nabla \cdot \epsilon_S \nabla S = 0. \quad (2c)$$

46 Here ϵ_Q with $Q \in \{\rho, \mathbf{m}, S\}$ indicates a viscosity, either physical or numerical, which will be specified later.

47 **Remark 2.1.** *When ϵ_ρ , $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}}$ and ϵ_S are constant, this viscous regularization coincides with the “monolithic*
 48 *regularization” discussed by Guermond and Popov in [32], but in general they are different. Nevertheless,*
 49 *both regularizations do not have a physical meaning: they serve as a numerical tool to resolve discontinuities*
 50 *and shocks.*

51 *2.2. Asymptotic limit*

Let us assume now that $\epsilon_\rho = \epsilon_S = 0$ and $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = \nu$ with ν being a nonnegative constant. Then, an asymptotic analysis (see, e.g., [33, 34, 23, 35]) reveals that when c^2 goes to infinity and ρ is constant, the system (2) tends to the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with the viscosity term in rotational form:

$$\partial_t(\rho \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho \mathbf{u}) + \nabla p + \mu \nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (3a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (3b)$$

52 with $\mu = \nu \rho$.

Only for constant viscosity, the rightmost term in (3a) coincides with the usual $-\mu \Delta \mathbf{u}$ as a consequence of the following identity:

$$-\mu \Delta \mathbf{u} = \mu (\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{u} - \nabla \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \mu \nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{u}.$$

53 This reformulation of the viscous stress tensor has been put forward for the first time by Nédélec in [36] and
 54 has been studied theoretically and numerically for the Stokes and the Navier-Stokes problems, for example,
 55 in [37, 38, 39, 40, 13, 14], without claiming completeness.

56 **Remark 2.2.** *We are considering the Laplace formulation of the viscous stress tensor, which is known to*
 57 *yield unphysical solutions in the presence of Navier slip boundary conditions on curved boundaries [41]. In*
 58 *the case of the rotational formulation of the Laplacian, this problem can be solved by adding an appropriate*
 59 *boundary term proportional to the Weingarten map (see the works of Mitrea and Monniaux [42] and Boon,*
 60 *Hitpmair, Tonnon and Zampa [43]), which is nonzero only on curved boundaries. For simplicity, in this*
 61 *work we consider only flat boundaries when dealing with Navier slip boundary conditions.*

62 *2.3. Lagrangian formulation and second order pressure wave equation*

Consider the original inviscid isentropic Euler system (1). Inserting the continuity equation (1a) into the momentum equation (1b) and making use of the definition of the Lagrangian derivative $d_t := \partial_t + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla$ leads to the following compact Lagrangian formulation of the equations in primitive variables:

$$d_t \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (4a)$$

$$\rho d_t \mathbf{u} + \nabla p = 0, \quad (4b)$$

$$d_t S = 0. \quad (4c)$$

63 Applying the Lagrangian derivative to (4a), taking the spatial divergence of (4b) and inserting one equation
 64 into the other leads to a nonlinear second order pressure wave equation of the type

$$d_{tt} \rho(p, S) - \nabla^2 p = f(\rho, \mathbf{u}, S, \nabla \rho, \nabla \mathbf{u}, \nabla S), \quad (5)$$

65 or, equivalently, since $d_t S = 0$ and since $\partial\rho/\partial p = 1/c^2$,

$$d_t \left(\frac{d_t p}{c^2} \right) - \nabla^2 p = f(\rho, \mathbf{u}, S, \nabla\rho, \nabla\mathbf{u}, \nabla S), \quad (6)$$

66 with $d_{tt} = d_t d_t$ and $f = \rho(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})^2 - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla\rho \cdot \nabla p + \rho \nabla\mathbf{u} : \nabla\mathbf{u}^T$ a function that depends on the state variables
 67 and their gradients, but not on their second order derivatives. It is interesting to see that for incompressible
 68 flows with $c \rightarrow \infty$, $\rho \rightarrow const.$ and $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rightarrow 0$ the function f tends to $f_{inc} = \rho \nabla\mathbf{u} : \nabla\mathbf{u}^T$, which is identical to
 69 the right hand side of the well-known pressure Poisson equation $-\nabla^2 p = \rho \nabla\mathbf{u} : \nabla\mathbf{u}^T$ of the *incompressible*
 70 Euler equations. In many semi-implicit schemes it is therefore common practice to repeat the above steps
 71 also at the discrete level in order to reduce the discrete continuity and momentum equations to a discrete
 72 nonlinear pressure wave equation, similar to (6), which after appropriate Newton linearization [44, 45] in
 73 the end requires only the solution of a sequence of symmetric and positive definite linear algebraic systems,
 74 see e.g. [21, 22, 24, 46, 44, 45, 25], and which naturally tends to the pressure Poisson equation of the
 75 incompressible Euler equations when the Mach number $M = \|\mathbf{u}\|/c$ tends to zero.

76 3. Numerical method

77 3.1. Time discretization

In our semi-implicit scheme the convection of momentum and entropy is treated explicitly, whereas the
 remaining terms are treated implicitly. For simplicity, we present a low order semi-implicit splitting, see e.g.
 [20, 21], with higher order in time achievable via the IMEX methodology, see e.g. [47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53].
 As anticipated in the introduction, we are going to use the density as a function of the pressure and the
 entropy. Therefore, our time discretization of (2) reads

$$\rho(p^{n+1}, S^{n+1}) + \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}^{n+1} = \rho^n, \quad (7a)$$

$$\mathbf{m}^{n+1} + \Delta t \nabla p^{n+1} - \Delta t \nabla (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}^{n+1}) + \Delta t \nabla \times (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \times \mathbf{m}^{n+1}) = \mathbf{m}^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho^n, \mathbf{m}^n), \quad (7b)$$

$$S^{n+1} - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\epsilon_S \nabla S^{n+1}) = S^n - \Delta t \frac{\mathbf{m}^n}{\rho^n} \cdot \nabla S^n. \quad (7c)$$

78 We solve (7a)-(7b) with the Newton method. For notational convenience, set $(c^2)^{n+1,l} = c^2(p^{n+1,l}, S^{n+1}) =$
 79 $\partial p / \partial \rho(p^{n+1,l}, S^{n+1})$, $\mathbf{m}^* = \mathbf{m}^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho^n, \mathbf{m}^n)$ and $\rho^{n+1,l} = \rho(p^{n+1,l}, S^{n+1})$, with $\rho^{n+1,0} = \rho^n$. With
 80 these conventions, and using the simple linearization of the density in terms of the unknown pressure

$$\rho(p^{n+1,l+1}, S^{n+1}) = \rho(p^{n+1,l}, S^{n+1}) + \partial\rho/\partial p(p^{n+1,l}, S^{n+1})(p^{n+1,l+1} - p^{n+1,l}), \quad (8)$$

since the entropy at the new time S^{n+1} is already known from (7c), the Newton iteration reads

$$\frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p^{n+1,l+1} + \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}^{n+1,l+1} = \rho^n - \rho^{n+1,l} + \frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p^{n+1,l}, \quad (9a)$$

$$\mathbf{m}^{n+1,l+1} + \Delta t \nabla p^{n+1,l+1} - \Delta t \nabla (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}^{n+1,l+1}) + \Delta t \nabla \times (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \times \mathbf{m}^{n+1,l+1}) = \mathbf{m}^*. \quad (9b)$$

81 Finally, we update the density:

$$\rho^{n+1} - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\epsilon_\rho \nabla \rho^{n+1}) = \rho^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}^{n+1}. \quad (10)$$

82 **Remark 3.1.** Note that the $\nabla \cdot (\epsilon_\rho \nabla \rho)$ term is neglected in (7a), but is present in (10). This is equivalent to
 83 a splitting of the density convection and diffusion terms. In this way, the nonlinear system (7) is considerably
 84 simplified.

3.2. Space discretization

3.2.1. Notation

We first introduce some notation. The L^2 scalar product of two scalar-valued or vector-valued functions is indicated by (\cdot, \cdot) . Let \mathcal{T}_h be a simplicial triangulation of the domain Ω . A generic element in \mathcal{T}_h is denoted by T ; its boundary is ∂T . A generic facet is denoted by e . We denote the L^2 product on D by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_D$ for $D \in \{\partial\Omega, \partial T, e\}$. We define the skeleton of the mesh as $\partial\mathcal{T}_h \doteq \bigcup_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \partial T$, in which each internal facet is counted twice, so that any function on $\partial\mathcal{T}_h$ is *double-valued* on each internal facet. We define the scalar product on $\partial\mathcal{T}_h$ as

$$\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h} \doteq \sum_{T \in \mathcal{T}_h} \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\partial T}.$$

Given a double-valued function $\widehat{v} \in L^2(\partial\mathcal{T}_h)$, we define its average and jump as the elements in $L^2(\partial\mathcal{T}_h)$, such that at a facet e we have

$$\begin{aligned} \{\!\!\{ \widehat{v} \}\!\!\}_{e^\pm} &\doteq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(\widehat{v}^+ + \widehat{v}^-) & \text{if } e = \partial T^+ \cap \partial T^- \text{ is an internal facet,} \\ \widehat{v}^+ & \text{if } e \text{ is a boundary facet;} \end{cases} \\ \llbracket \widehat{v} \rrbracket_{e^\pm} &\doteq \begin{cases} \pm(\widehat{v}^+ - \widehat{v}^-) & \text{if } e = \partial T^+ \cap \partial T^- \text{ is an internal facet,} \\ 0 & \text{if } e \text{ is a boundary facet.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The average is single-valued, i.e. $\{\!\!\{ \widehat{v} \}\!\!\}_{e^+} = \{\!\!\{ \widehat{v} \}\!\!\}_{e^-}$, while the jump is *single-valued up to its sign*, i.e. $\llbracket \widehat{v} \rrbracket_{e^+} = -\llbracket \widehat{v} \rrbracket_{e^-}$.

We will consider the following finite element spaces. Let Σ_{r+1} be the space of classical continuous Lagrange finite elements of degree $r+1$ when the dimension is two and the space of Nédélec edge-elements of first kind of degree $r+1$ [54] when the dimension is three. We will also indicate by RT_r and dP_r the spaces of Raviart-Thomas [55] and discontinuous finite elements respectively. In particular note that $\nabla \times \Sigma_{r+1} \subset \text{RT}_r$ and $\nabla \cdot \text{RT}_r = \text{dP}_r$. For a finite element space $V \in \{\Sigma_{r+1}, \text{RT}_r\}$, we denote by \mathring{V} its subspace with essential boundary conditions. Finally, let $a_\epsilon : \text{dP}_r \times \text{dP}_r \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the classical symmetric interior-penalty bilinear form associated to the $-\nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla)$ operator introduced by Arnold [56]:

$$a_\epsilon(p_h, q_h) \doteq (\epsilon \nabla p_h, \nabla q_h)_{\mathcal{T}_h} + \left\langle \frac{\zeta \epsilon}{h} \llbracket p_h \rrbracket, \llbracket q_h \rrbracket \right\rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h} - \langle \{\!\!\{ \epsilon \nabla p_h \}\!\!\} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \llbracket q_h \rrbracket \rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h} - \langle \{\!\!\{ \epsilon \nabla q_h \}\!\!\} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \llbracket p_h \rrbracket \rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h}.$$

Here ζ is a user-defined parameter, that should be large enough to ensure coercivity of the bilinear form $a_\epsilon(p_h, q_h)$.

3.2.2. Path-conservative DG scheme for the entropy

In eqn. (2c) the entropy transport equation is used instead of the total energy conservation law, hence we cannot expect shock waves to be correct for large shock Mach numbers, see [57, 58]. This is because non-conservative systems lack a definition of weak solution in the presence of discontinuities and since for the correct computation of shock waves in fluids total energy conservation is mandatory. In this work, we therefore deliberately only consider *weakly compressible* isentropic flows, with Mach numbers ranging from zero to about unity. This is in accordance with the work of Springel [59], in which it is shown that the error in shock waves computed with the entropy formulation is negligible when the Mach number is below 1.1. In general, the appropriate numerical discretization of non-conservative hyperbolic equations still remains a challenge. From the theoretical side, a possible solution to the problem has been proposed by Dal Maso, LeFloch and Murat [60], who introduced a theory (called DLM theory in the following) of weak solutions using paths in phase-space. The DLM theory has inspired Parés to develop a theoretical framework of path-conservative numerical methods [61]. This framework has been used to design Finite Volume methods for non-conservative systems by Parés, Castro and collaborators [62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67]. The first path-conservative Discontinuous Galerkin finite element methods have been proposed in [68, 69] and [70].

107 Recall that the velocity \mathbf{u} is a function of density and momentum, i.e. Let $\mathbf{Q} = (\rho, \mathbf{m})$. Then $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{Q})$
 108 is a function of \mathbf{Q} , since $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{m}/\rho$. Let $\Psi(\mathbf{Q}^+, \mathbf{Q}^-)$ be a path in phase space joining \mathbf{Q}^- and \mathbf{Q}^+ , that
 109 is $\Psi(0) = \mathbf{Q}^+$ and $\Psi(1) = \mathbf{Q}^-$. At each mesh interface, we look for a ‘‘Roe-type normal velocity’’ $\widehat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{n}}$
 110 satisfying the generalized Rankine-Hugoniot conditions:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{n}} \llbracket S_h \rrbracket = \int_0^1 \mathbf{u}(\Psi(\mathbf{Q}^+, \mathbf{Q}^-)) \cdot \mathbf{n} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial s} \, dS. \quad (11)$$

111 In this work we choose the segment path $\Psi(s) = (1-s)\mathbf{Q}^+ + s\mathbf{Q}^-$, which yields the following expression
 112 for $\widehat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{n}}$:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{n}} = \int_0^1 \mathbf{u}(\Psi(\mathbf{Q}^+, \mathbf{Q}^-)) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS. \quad (12)$$

113 The integral in (12) can be approximated with a quadrature rule. In our numerical experiments we have
 114 noticed that the midpoint rule is sufficient to preserve the accuracy and correctness of the scheme. Then,
 115 the weak problem associated to each time-step reads as follows. Note that for the discretization of linearly
 116 degenerate fields, the choice of the path has only little influence on the numerical solution, see e.g. [68],
 117 and Section 4.4. Usually in the context of shallow water-type equations or for the Baer-Nunziato model
 118 of compressible multi-phase flows, the choice of the segment path provides additional properties of the
 119 numerical method such as well-balancing or preservation of uniform flow, see e.g. [71, 72, 73, 70].

Weak problem. Find S_h^{n+1} such that

$$(S_h^{n+1}, R_h) + \Delta t a_{\epsilon_S}(S_h^{n+1}, R_h) = (S_h^n, R_h) - \Delta t \left(\frac{\mathbf{m}_h^n}{\rho_h^n} \cdot \nabla S_h^n, R_h \right) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \langle (\widehat{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \widehat{\mathbf{n}} - s_{\max}) \llbracket S_h^n \rrbracket, R_h \rangle_{\partial \mathcal{T}_h}$$

120 for each $R_h \in \mathcal{dP}_r$.

121 Here $s_{\max} \doteq \max \left(2 \left| \frac{\mathbf{m}_h^+}{\rho_h^+} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right|, 2 \left| \frac{\mathbf{m}_h^-}{\rho_h^-} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right| \right)$. Note that the matrix associated to this linear system is
 122 symmetric positive definite.

123 3.2.3. Convection of the momentum

124 For the convection of the momentum we employ a standard DG discretization. Let \mathbf{m}_h^* be the solution
 125 of

$$(\mathbf{m}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h) = (\mathbf{m}_h^n, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t (\mathcal{F}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho_h^n, \mathbf{m}_h^n), \nabla_h \mathbf{v}_h) + \langle \widehat{\mathcal{F}}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho_h^n, \mathbf{m}_h^n) \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{v}_h \rangle_{\partial \mathcal{T}_h}. \quad (13)$$

126 At an interface $e = \partial T^+ \cap \partial T^-$, in order to discretize the nonlinear convective terms we use a Ducros-type
 127 numerical flux with a dissipative term:

$$\widehat{\mathcal{F}}(\rho_h, \mathbf{m}_h) \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{m}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \{ \mathbf{m}_h / \rho_h \} + \frac{1}{2} s_{\max} \llbracket \mathbf{m}_h \rrbracket, \quad (14)$$

128 with s_{\max} is defined as in the previous section.

129 3.2.4. Mixed finite element discretization of the momentum-pressure system

130 We introduce the ‘‘momentum vorticity’’ $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \times \mathbf{m}$. We approximate $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ with Σ_{r+1} , \mathbf{m} with Raviart-
 131 Thomas elements RT_r [55] and p with element-wise discontinuous polynomials \mathcal{dP}_r . Then, at each Newton
 132 iteration we solve the following linear system.

Weak problem. Find $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h \in \Sigma_{r+1}$, $\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1, l+1} \in \text{RT}_r$, $p_h^{n+1, l+1} \in \mathcal{dP}_r$ satisfying

$$\left(\frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1, l}} p_h^{n+1, l+1}, q_h \right) + \Delta t (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1, l+1}, q_h) = \left(\rho_h^n - \rho^{n+1, l} + \frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1, l}} p_h^{n+1, l}, q_h \right), \quad (15a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1, l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t (p_h^{n+1, l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) \\ & + \Delta t (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1, l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) + \Delta t (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1, l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h) - \langle \bar{p}, \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial \Omega}, \end{aligned} \quad (15b)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1, l+1}, \mathbf{z}_h \right) - (\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1, l+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) = \langle \mathbf{n} \times \bar{\mathbf{m}}, \mathbf{z}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (15c)$$

133 for each $q_h \in \mathcal{dP}_r$, $\mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbf{RT}_r$ and $\mathbf{z}_h \in \Sigma_{r+1}$.

134 **Remark 3.2.** This choice of spaces corresponds to “outflow” boundary conditions:

$$(p - \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m})|_{\partial\Omega} = \bar{p}, \quad \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{m}|_{\partial\Omega} = \mathbf{n} \times \bar{\mathbf{m}}. \quad (16)$$

135 If we choose the spaces $\overset{\circ}{\Sigma}_{r+1}$, $\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{RT}}_r$ in place of Σ_{r+1} and \mathbf{RT}_r , we obtain the nonstandard “slip” boundary
136 conditions:

$$\mathbf{m}|_{\partial\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0, \quad \mathbf{n} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{m})|_{\partial\Omega} = 0. \quad (17)$$

137 See Mitrea and Monniaux [42] for a discussion on how these boundary conditions relate to the standard
138 Navier slip ones. Finally, the choice Σ_{r+1} and $\overset{\circ}{\mathbf{RT}}_r$ yields Dirichlet boundary conditions (which include both
139 those commonly referred as “wall” and “inflow”):

$$\mathbf{m}|_{\partial\Omega} = \bar{\mathbf{m}}. \quad (18)$$

140 In this latter case, the inclusion $\nabla \times \Sigma_{r+1} \subset \overset{\circ}{\mathbf{RT}}_r$ is false. This issue is the source of the suboptimal
141 convergence rate of ω_h and p_h shown by Arnold, Falk and Gopalakrishnan in [39].

142 When the Newton method has converged, we update the density solving the problem

$$(\rho_h^{n+1}, q_h) + \Delta t a_{\epsilon_\rho}(\rho_h^{n+1}, q_h) = (\rho_h^n, q_h) - \Delta t (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1}, q_h). \quad (19)$$

143 We can immediately deduce the following conservation properties of our scheme.

Theorem 3.1. Assume that $\mathbf{m}_h \cdot \mathbf{n}$ and $\mathbf{n} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h$ vanish on the boundary of Ω and $\epsilon_\rho = 0$. If the Newton iteration (15) converges, then the resulting scheme conserves mass locally and momentum globally, that is:

$$\int_T \rho_h^{n+1} \, d\mathbf{x} = \int_T \rho_h^n \, d\mathbf{x} + \Delta t \int_{\partial T} \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS, \quad \forall T \in \mathcal{T}_h, \quad (20)$$

$$\int_\Omega \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1} \, d\mathbf{x} = \int_\Omega \mathbf{m}_h^n \, d\mathbf{x}. \quad (21)$$

Furthermore, if either $\epsilon_\rho = 0$ or $\nabla \rho \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$, mass is conserved also globally:

$$\int_\Omega \rho^{n+1} \, d\mathbf{x} = \int_\Omega \rho^n \, d\mathbf{x}.$$

Proof. When $\epsilon_\rho = 0$, equation (19) reduces to the simple update $\rho_h^{n+1} = \rho_h^n - \Delta t \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1}$, since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{RT}_r = \mathcal{dP}_r$. The first property follows then from the Gauss theorem. To prove the second property, take $\mathbf{v}_h = \mathbf{e}_i$ in (13) and (15b). Clearly, the terms involving derivatives of \mathbf{e}_i vanish. It remains to show that $\langle \widehat{\mathcal{F}}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho_h^n, \mathbf{m}_h^n) \cdot \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{e}_i \rangle_{\mathcal{T}_h}$ and $(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{e}_i)$ vanish as well. The first term is zero since \mathbf{e}_i is continuous and $\widehat{\mathcal{F}}_{\mathbf{m}}(\rho_h^n, \mathbf{m}_h^n) \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is single-valued at internal facets and vanishes on the boundary. For the second one, the claim follows from the simple computation

$$\begin{aligned} (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{e}_i) &= \int_\Omega \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \, d\mathbf{x} \\ &= \int_\Omega \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1} \times \mathbf{e}_i) \, d\mathbf{x} \\ &= \int_{\partial\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1} \times \mathbf{e}_i) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS \\ &= \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{n} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}) \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \, dS \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

144 In the last step we have used the fact that $\mathbf{n} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h$ vanishes on the boundary. Finally, if $\epsilon_\rho = 0$, the global
 145 conservation of mass follows from the local one since $\mathbf{m}_h \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is single-valued at internal facets and vanishes
 146 on the boundary. On the other hand, if $\epsilon_\rho \neq 0$ and $\nabla \rho \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$, the claim follows by taking $q_h = 1$ in
 147 (19) since $a_{\epsilon_\rho}(\rho_h^{n+1}, 1) = 0$. \square

148 3.2.5. Efficient decoupling of the vorticity from the pressure

149 Taking $\mathbf{v}_h = \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h$ with $\mathbf{z}_h \in \Sigma_{r+1}$ in (15b) and using $\nabla \cdot \nabla \times = 0$, we obtain

$$(\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) + \Delta t(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) - \langle \bar{p}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega}. \quad (22)$$

150 Taking the sum of (22) with (15c), we obtain a single decoupled equation for the vorticity.

151 **Weak problem.** Find $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1} \in \Sigma_{r+1}$ satisfying

$$\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{z}_h \right) + \Delta t(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) - \langle \bar{p}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega} + \langle \mathbf{n} \times \bar{\mathbf{m}}, \mathbf{z}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (23)$$

152 for each $\mathbf{z}_h \in \Sigma_{r+1}$.

153 Note that the matrix associated to this linear system is symmetric positive definite. Once we have
 154 computed $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}$, we can compute momentum and pressure as follows.

Weak problem. Find $\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1} \in \text{RT}_r$ and $p_h^{n+1,l+1} \in \text{dP}_r$ satisfying

$$\left(\frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p_h^{n+1,l+1}, q_h \right) + \Delta t(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, q_h) = \left(\rho_h^n - \rho^{n+1,l} + \frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p_h^{n+1,l}, q_h \right), \quad (24a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t(p_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) \\ + \Delta t(\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h) - \langle \bar{p}, \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega} - \Delta t(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h), \end{aligned} \quad (24b)$$

155 for each $\mathbf{v}_h \in \text{RT}_r$ and $q_h \in \text{dP}_r$.

Remark 3.3. The same splitting procedure can be applied in the case of nonstandard slip boundary conditions since $\nabla \times \Sigma_{r+1} \subset \text{RT}_r$. On the other side, the case of Dirichlet boundary condition is more delicate, since we cannot take $\mathbf{v}_h = \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h$ due to $\nabla \times \Sigma_{r+1} \not\subset \text{RT}_r$, as already explained in Remark 3.2. We can circumvent this obstacle with the following trick. Instead of imposing the boundary condition $\mathbf{m}|_{\partial\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ essentially, we impose it via a Lagrange multiplier \hat{p}_h belonging to the space of discontinuous polynomials on the boundary:

$$\widehat{M}_h = \{\hat{q}_h \in L^2(\partial\Omega) \mid \hat{q}_h|_e \in \mathcal{P}_r(e) \forall e \subset \partial\Omega\}.$$

Using this space, we can rewrite equation (15b) as the following equivalent system: find $(\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \hat{p}_h) \in \text{RT}_r \times \widehat{M}_h$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t(p_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) \\ + \Delta t(\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) + \Delta t(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) + \langle \hat{p}_h, \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega} = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h), \end{aligned} \quad (25a)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \hat{q}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \quad (25b)$$

156 for each $(\mathbf{v}_h, \hat{q}_h) \in \text{RT}_r \times \widehat{M}_h$. Now it is possible to take $\mathbf{v}_h = \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h$ in (25a), obtaining the following
 157 equation for $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}$:

$$\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{z}_h \right) + \Delta t(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) + \langle \hat{p}_h, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega} = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) + \langle \mathbf{n} \times \bar{\mathbf{m}}, \mathbf{z}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (26)$$

158 The presence of \hat{p} makes equation (26) an underdetermined problem. To recover well-posedness, we take
 159 either $\hat{p}_h = \bar{p}$, when the boundary pressure is known, or $\hat{p}_h = p_h^n|_{\partial\Omega}$. Then, the momentum and the pressure
 160 are obtained as in the other cases.

Linear algebra and hybridization. We briefly comment on the algebraic structure of system (24) and the possible solution strategy. Let $M_{c^2}^p$ and $M^{\mathbf{m}}$ the (weighted) mass matrices associated to p and \mathbf{m} respectively, and let D and S be the div and div-div matrices. Then, the matrix G associated to (24) reads

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} M_{c^2}^p & D \\ -D^T & M^{\mathbf{m}} + S \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now, since $M_{c^2}^p$ is block diagonal, it can be inverted cheaply and we can consider its Schur complement $\tilde{G}_{\mathbf{m}} = M + S + D^T(M_{c^2}^p)^{-1}D$ which is symmetric and positive definite. However, when $c^2 \rightarrow \infty$, the matrix $M_{c^2}^p$ tends to 0 and $\tilde{G}_{\mathbf{m}}$ becomes ill-conditioned, so this strategy is impractical for large values of c^2 . As a remedy, we introduce hybridization, that is, we break the normal continuity of the space RT_r and we enforce it via a Lagrange multiplier. Let $\widetilde{\text{RT}}_r$ be the ‘‘broken version’’ of RT_r , that is $\widetilde{\text{RT}}_r$ is the space of L^2 functions on Ω such that the restriction on each element is a Raviart-Thomas polynomial of degree r . Now, given a facet e , $\mathbf{v}_h|_e \cdot \mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{P}_{r-1}(e)$ for $\mathbf{v}_h \in \text{RT}_r$, where $\mathcal{P}_{r-1}(e)$ is the space of polynomials of degree $r-1$ on e (for a proof, see Proposition 2.3.3 in [74]). It follows that the normal continuity of \mathbf{m}_h can be imposed via a Lagrange multiplier λ_h in the space

$$M_h \doteq \prod_{e \in \mathcal{E}_h} \mathcal{P}_{r-1}(e).$$

Define also the space $\mathring{M}_{\bar{p},h}$ as the subspace of M_h ‘‘with boundary conditions’’:

$$\mathring{M}_{\bar{p},h} \doteq \{\lambda_h \in M_h \mid \langle \lambda_h, \xi_h \rangle_e = \langle \bar{p}, \xi_h \rangle_e \forall \xi \in \mathcal{P}_r(e) \forall e \subset \partial\Omega\}.$$

161 The hybridized formulation with outflow boundary conditions reads:

Weak problem. Find $\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1} \in \widetilde{\text{RT}}_r$, $p_h^{n+1,l+1} \in \text{d}\mathcal{P}_r$ and $\lambda_h \in \mathring{M}_{\bar{p},h}$ satisfying

$$\left(\frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p_h^{n+1,l+1}, q_h \right) + \Delta t (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, q_h) = \left(\rho_h^n - \rho^{n+1,l} + \frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,l}} p_h^{n+1,l}, q_h \right), \quad (27a)$$

$$(\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t (p_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) \quad (27b)$$

$$+ \Delta t (\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) + \langle \lambda_h, \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h} = (\mathbf{m}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,l+1}, \mathbf{v}_h), \quad (27c)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,l+1} \cdot \mathbf{n}, \xi_h \rangle_{\partial\mathcal{T}_h} = 0,$$

162 for each $\mathbf{v}_h \in \widetilde{\text{RT}}_r$, $q_h \in \text{d}\mathcal{P}_r$ and $\xi_h \in \mathring{M}_{0,h}$.

163 **Remark 3.4.** Note that in the hybridized formulation (27), the boundary condition $(p - \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{m})|_{\partial\Omega} = \bar{p}$ is
164 imposed essentially, rather than naturally. Then, as it is customary in this situation, we consider the space
165 $\mathring{M}_{0,h}$ with homogeneous boundary conditions for the test functions.

166 **Remark 3.5.** In the case of either Dirichlet or slip boundary conditions, the space $\mathring{M}_{\bar{p},h}$ must be replaced
167 with M_h .

The resulting matrix has the block structure

$$\tilde{G} = \begin{pmatrix} M_{c^2}^p & \tilde{D} & 0 \\ \tilde{D}^T & -(\tilde{M}^{\mathbf{m}} + S) & \tilde{B}^T \\ 0 & \tilde{B} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Defining the matrices

$$L \doteq \begin{pmatrix} M_{c^2}^p & \tilde{D} \\ \tilde{D}^T & -(\tilde{M}^{\mathbf{m}} + S) \end{pmatrix}, \quad C \doteq (0 \quad I),$$

with I being the identity matrix, we can rewrite \tilde{G} as

$$\tilde{G} = \begin{pmatrix} L & C^T \tilde{B}^T \\ \tilde{B}C & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

168 In the parlance of Cockburn, Gopalakrishnan and Lazarov [75], L is the “local solver” matrix and it is block-
169 diagonal. Moreover, L remains invertible even when $c^2 \rightarrow \infty$. We can then consider its Schur complement
170 $\tilde{B}CL^{-1}C^T\tilde{B}^T$, which is symmetric and negative definite, as we now show.

171 **Lemma 3.1.** *The matrix $\tilde{B}CL^{-1}C^T\tilde{B}^T$ is symmetric negative definite.*

Proof. In this proof, given a generic finite element function v in a finite element space V , we denote by \vec{v}
the associated vector of degrees of freedom. The symmetry is evident since L is symmetric. We prove the
negative definiteness. Given $\vec{\xi}$, let $\begin{pmatrix} \vec{q} \\ \vec{v} \end{pmatrix} = -L^{-1}C^T\tilde{B}^T\vec{\xi}$, that is

$$\begin{aligned} -(\tilde{M}^m + S)\vec{v} + \tilde{D}^T\vec{q} &= -\tilde{B}^T\vec{\xi}, \\ M_{c^2}^p\vec{q} + \tilde{D}\vec{v} &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we remark that $(\vec{q}, \vec{v}) = 0$ if and only if $\vec{\xi} = 0$, due to the invertibility of L and the injectivity
of \tilde{B}^T . Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\xi}^T \tilde{B}CL^{-1}C^T\tilde{B}^T\vec{\xi} &= -\vec{\xi}^T \tilde{B}C \begin{pmatrix} \vec{q} \\ \vec{v} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= -\vec{\xi}^T \tilde{B}\vec{v} \\ &= -\vec{v}^T(\tilde{M}^m + S)\vec{v} + \vec{q}^T\tilde{D}\vec{v} \\ &= -\vec{v}^T(\tilde{M}^m + S)\vec{v} - \vec{q}^T M_{c^2}^p\vec{q}. \end{aligned}$$

172 The claim follows from the positive-definiteness of $\tilde{M}^m + S$ and $M_{c^2}^p$. □

173 **Remark 3.6.** *We remark that hybridization of (23) is possible (see [76]), but it is difficult to implement
174 and does not yield a significant advantage, since the matrix associated to (23) is already symmetric positive
175 definite.*

176 Our reasons for using the Schur complement in order to reduce the original nonsymmetric pressure-
177 velocity system (25) to a symmetric system for the pressure only are the following:

- 178 1. using the Schur complement reduces the number of unknowns, from the degrees of freedom necessary
179 to represent 3 fields for the velocity vector and one scalar pressure field to only the degrees of freedom
180 of one scalar pressure field;
- 181 2. the use of the Schur complement and therefore the reduction of the mixed pressure-velocity system to
182 a symmetric problem for the pressure alone is standard in the literature on semi-implicit schemes for
183 incompressible and compressible flows and mirrors at the discrete level the solution of the nonlinear
184 second order pressure wave equation (6), see e.g. [77, 78, 79, 21, 80, 22, 35, 23, 24, 81, 25, 82] and
185 references therein; in the present paper we therefore naturally follow this well-established tradition;
- 186 3. the final symmetric linear algebraic systems resulting from our discretization can be easily solved
187 via a matrix-free conjugate gradient (CG) method [83], which is also very simple to parallelize on
188 modern distributed memory supercomputers via MPI, while more general nonsymmetric linear systems
189 require the use of more complex and more expensive iterative solvers in terms of memory and / or
190 CPU time, such as the GMRES method [84] which needs to store previous matrix-vector products
191 in the computer memory, or the BiCGStab method [85] that requires two matrix-vector product
192 evaluations per iteration. In contrast, the CG method does *not* need to store any previous matrix-
193 vector product and only requires *one* matrix-vector product evaluation per iteration; in case of a
194 parallel implementation, GMRES and BiCGStab require also more MPI communications compared to
195 CG.

196 However, we emphasize that the reader may of course also directly solve the original system (25), without
 197 hybridization technique and without Schur complement.

198 3.3. *A posteriori limiting via artificial viscosity*

199 We now discuss the choices of ϵ_Q with $Q \in \{\rho, \mathbf{m}, S\}$. We follow the *a posteriori* MOOD concept
 200 originally introduced by Clain, Diot and Loubère [26, 27, 28] for finite volume methods. This idea has been
 201 successfully applied to high order DG methods [86, 87, 88] to construct *a posteriori* subcell limiters, and for
 202 staggered semi-implicit DG methods it has been successfully used by Tavelli and Dumbser in [29]. Recently,
 203 we have shown that the MOOD paradigm is effective also for compatible finite elements [30]. The MOOD
 204 strategy consists of three steps:

- 205 1. Computation of a so-called *candidate solution* at time $n + 1$ without the use of any limiting and/or
 206 artificial viscosity;
- 207 2. Detection of troubled cells by violation of numerical and/or physical admissibility criteria;
- 208 3. Re-computation of the solution with limiting/artificial viscosity on the troubled cells.

209 Following [29], our detection criterion is based on a discrete maximum principle. Let W be a scalar function
 210 depending possibly on $\{\rho, \mathbf{m}, S\}$. Then, we say that W satisfies the relaxed discrete maximum principle on
 211 the element $T \in \mathcal{T}_h$ if

$$\min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{N}(T)} W(\mathbf{y}, t^n) - \delta_T \leq W(\mathbf{x}, t^n) \leq \max_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{N}(T)} W(\mathbf{y}, t^n) + \delta_T, \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in T. \quad (28)$$

212 Here $\mathcal{N}(T)$ is the set made of the Voronoi neighbors of T and T itself, and δ_T is a relaxation parameter,
 213 which is defined as follows

$$\delta_T = \max \left(\delta_0, \eta \left(\max_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{N}(T)} W(\mathbf{y}, t^n) - \min_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{N}(T)} W(\mathbf{y}, t^n) \right) \right) \quad (29)$$

214 with δ_0 and η user-defined parameters. In this work we choose $\delta_0 = 10^{-4}$ and $\eta = 10^{-3}$. Then we set

$$\epsilon_Q|_T = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} h s_{\max} & \text{if (29) is violated on } T, \\ \bar{\epsilon} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

215 with s_{\max} an estimate of the maximum wavespeed in the full system and $\bar{\epsilon}$ being a small value to avoid
 216 division by zero.

217 3.4. *Summary of the algorithm*

218 The final algorithm can be summarized in the following steps:

- 219 1. Compute S_h^{n+1} via the path-conservative DG scheme and $\epsilon_S = 0$;
- 220 2. Compute ϵ_S as in (30) with $W = S$;
- 221 3. Repeat Step 1 with the new ϵ_S ;
- 222 4. Compute \mathbf{m}_h^{n+1} , p_h^{n+1} and ρ_h^{n+1} with the Newton iteration (15) with $\epsilon_\rho = \epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = 0$. In particular at
 223 each iteration, we solve (23) and (27).
- 224 5. Compute ϵ_ρ as in (30) with $W = \rho$;
- 225 6. Repeat Step 4 with $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = \epsilon_\rho$ with ϵ_ρ computed in the previous Step.

226 *3.5. Incompressible limit scheme*

227 In this section, we describe a scheme for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with constant density
 228 and viscosity. Moreover, we show that this scheme is the limit of the method introduced in the previous
 229 sections when the density is constant and the Mach number goes to zero. In particular, let $\mathbf{u}_h^* = \mathbf{m}_h^*/\rho$
 230 where \mathbf{m}_h^* is defined in (13). Then, the vorticity, the velocity and the pressure at time t^{n+1} are obtained
 231 solving the following problem.

Weak problem. Find $(\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, p_h^{n+1}) \in (\Sigma_{r+1} \times \text{RT}_r \times \text{dP}_r)$ satisfying

$$\left(\frac{1}{\mu} \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{z}_h \right) - (\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) = \langle \bar{\mathbf{u}}_h \times \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{z}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (31a)$$

$$(\rho \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) + \Delta t (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t (p_h^{n+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h) = (\rho \mathbf{u}_h^*, \mathbf{v}_h) - \Delta t \langle \bar{p}, \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} \rangle_{\partial\Omega}, \quad (31b)$$

$$(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, q_h) = 0, \quad (31c)$$

232 for each $(\mathbf{z}_h, \mathbf{v}_h, q_h) \in (\Sigma_{r+1} \times \text{RT}_r \times \text{dP}_r)$.

233 We prove now that in the zero Mach number limit, the Newton method (15) converges in one iteration
 234 and its solution coincides with the solution of (31).

235 **Theorem 3.2.** Assume that $\rho_h^n = \rho$ is constant in space and $\frac{1}{(c^2)^{n+1,0}} = 0$. Assume moreover that $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = \mu/\rho$
 236 with μ being a constant. Then, let $\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,1}$, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,1}$ and $p_h^{n+1,1}$ be solutions of (15) with $l = 0$. Then
 237 $\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} = \frac{\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,1}}{\rho}$, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_h^n = \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1,1}$ and $p^{n+1} = p^{n+1,1}$ solve (31).

Proof. First, note that \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} belongs to RT_r since $\mathbf{m}_h^{n+1,1} \in \text{RT}_r$ and ρ is a constant. Under the assumptions
 of the Theorem and $\rho^{n+1,0} = \rho_h^n$ we obtain that (15a) reduces to

$$\Delta t (\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}), q_h) = 0,$$

which is equivalent to (31c) since ρ is constant. Moreover, this implies that the div-div term in (15b)
 vanishes, and therefore (15) reduces to (31b). Similarly, taking $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = \mu/\rho$, (15c) reduces to

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\mu} \boldsymbol{\omega}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{z}_h \right) - (\rho \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \nabla \times \mathbf{z}_h) = \langle \rho \bar{\mathbf{u}} \times \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{z}_h \rangle_{\partial\Omega},$$

238 which is (31a) multiplied by ρ , concluding the proof. \square

Remark 3.7. We briefly discuss how the boundary conditions discussed in Remark 3.2 behave in the in-
 compressible limit. In particular, when ρ is a known positive constant and $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = 0$, outflow (16), slip (17)
 and Dirichlet (18) boundary conditions reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} p|_{\partial\Omega} &= \bar{p}, & \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} &= \mathbf{n} \times \bar{\mathbf{u}} & (\text{outflow}) \\ \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0, & \mathbf{n} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{u})|_{\partial\Omega} &= \bar{\mathbf{u}}, & (\text{slip}) \\ \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} &= 0, & & & (\text{Dirichlet}) \end{aligned}$$

239 respectively, recovering the classical boundary conditions for Navier-Stokes equations.

240 The scheme (31) is novel, as the considered combination of the reformulation of the equations, the
 241 compatible finite element spaces, the semi-implicit time discretization and the employed hybridization tech-
 242 niques has never appeared in the literature before. Nevertheless, our method has many analogies with
 243 some existing schemes for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations, which we now highlight. We confine
 244 ourselves to $H(\text{div})$ -based methods for unsteady incompressible flows that preserve $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ exactly point-
 245 wise everywhere. In particular, we neglect discontinuous Galerkin methods that achieve this property via
 246 postprocessing, such as those devised by Cockburn and collaborators [89, 4, 90]. We discuss the following
 247 ingredients:

- 248 • Spatial discretization of the convective term;
- 249 • Spatial discretization of the viscous term;
- 250 • Time discretization.

Convective term. Our DG-based discretization of the convective term coincides with the one proposed by Guzmán et al. in [5]. An alternative would be rewriting the convective term using Lamb's identity:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) = \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = \rho(\nabla \times \mathbf{u}) \times \mathbf{u} + \frac{1}{2} \rho \nabla(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u})$$

Then, the quadratic term $\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{u})$ is incorporated in the pressure variable. This strategy has been used in [11, 12, 15, 7, 13]. Another alternative discretization of the convective term recently appeared in [14]. The weak formulation of the convective term is rewritten as follows assuming vanishing boundary conditions for the velocity:

$$\int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\mathbf{x} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\mathbf{x} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_h \cdot \mathbf{u} \, d\mathbf{x}$$

251 The term on the right-hand side is then discretized using appropriate projection operators. The resulting
 252 methods are conforming (no jump terms appear), however no upwinding is present. Therefore implicit
 253 timestepping is mandatory, leading to the solution of a nonlinear nonsymmetric system at each time step.
 254 On the other side, DG methods allow dissipative upwinding and therefore are stable also with explicit time
 255 discretizations. Finally, we mention the nondissipative upwind DG method of Natale and Cotter [6]. The
 256 convection term is treated as a discrete Lie derivative as defined by Heumann et al. in [91]:

$$(\rho \mathbf{u}_h, \nabla \times (\mathbf{u}_h \times \mathbf{v}_h) - \mathbf{u}_h \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h)_{\mathcal{T}_h} + \langle \mathbf{n} \times \rho \mathbf{u}_h^{\text{upw}}, \llbracket \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{v}_h \rrbracket \rangle_{\partial \mathcal{T}_h}. \quad (32)$$

257 Note that when $\mathbf{v}_h = \mathbf{u}_h$, (32) vanishes. As a consequence, this spatial discretization, when coupled with
 258 a midpoint rule in time, conserves the energy, which is remarkable for an upwind scheme. Finally, we
 259 remark that many of the alternatives mentioned here assume that the density is constant, which is not our
 260 case in general. See Gawlik and Gay-Balmaz [7] for a rotational form of the advection term in the case of
 261 nonconstant density.

262 *Viscous term.* As an alternative to the vorticity-based reformulation of the viscous term used also in [11, 12,
 263 13, 14, 15], it is possible to use hybridizable discontinuous Galerkin methods (HDG), as done, for example,
 264 in [8] or discontinuous Galerkin (DG) [10].

265 *Time discretization.* Our simple semi-implicit time discretization necessitates of the solution of only symmetric
 266 positive definite linear systems. Moreover, the implicit treatment of the viscous term avoids a quadratic
 267 CFL restriction of the time step size. On the other side, all the methods [5, 11, 6, 7, 12, 13, 14, 15]
 268 treat the convection term implicitly, needing the solution of a *nonsymmetric* system at each time step. The
 269 only scheme that avoids the solution of a nonsymmetric system is the semi-implicit scheme proposed by
 270 Lehrenfeld and Schöberl [8], which circumvents the problem via a pseudo-implicit approach. We mention
 271 also the scheme of Fu [10], which treats the both the convective term and viscous term explicitly. This latter
 272 method is very cheap, since it requires only the solution of one single symmetric linear system at each time
 273 iteration, but it is not suitable for low Reynolds number flows. We underline that our time discretization
 274 combined with our choice of numerical flux in the convection term is not energy conserving. However, we
 275 will show in Section 4 that the energy dissipation is remarkably small and it actually helps in avoiding
 276 spurious oscillations arising from under resolved scales.

277 3.6. Comparison with other methods

278 We briefly compare the proposed method with the ones for compressible flows [7, 16, 17, 18, 19] already
279 mentioned in the introduction to emphasize the novelties of our approach.

280 We start with the works by Gawlik and Gay-Balmaz [7, 16, 17]. All these methods discretize directly
281 the velocity \mathbf{u} and not the momentum \mathbf{m} , use a fully-implicit time discretization and lack a shock-capturing
282 term, i.e. these methods are not suitable for the computation of flows with discontinuities, while ours is.
283 Reference [7] deals with incompressible inviscid fluids with variable density, in [16] barotropic fluids are
284 considered, where pressure is only a function of the density, while in our approach we consider weakly
285 compressible flows in which the pressure depends on both, density and entropy. The method proposed in
286 [17] is more general, since it discretizes heat conducting viscous fluids, but it approximates the velocity
287 with continuous Lagrange finite elements, and therefore it does *not* converge to an exactly divergence-free
288 method in the low Mach number limit, while the method presented in this paper does.

289 On the other side, the Versatile Mixed Method introduced by Miller and Williams [18] is asymptotic-
290 preserving and converges to an exactly divergence-free method for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equa-
291 tions. However, the authors consider a density-velocity-temperature formulation and a fully-implicit time-
292 discretization, which results in a large nonlinear nonsymmetric system to be solved at each time iteration.
293 Moreover, only linear stabilizations are employed, which are not enough to resolve shocks and mitigate spu-
294 rious oscillations when nonsmooth solutions are considered. In fact, Miller and Williams consider numerical
295 tests with Mach number up to 0.5, whereas we are able to resolve flows with Mach number above one, as
296 we will demonstrate in Section 4.3. We conjecture that if the equations are reformulated with conservative
297 variables and a nonlinear stabilization mechanism is added, such as the one proposed in this paper, [18] can
298 be extended to the fully compressible Navier-Stokes system at all Mach numbers.

299 Finally, neglecting the magnetic contribution, the equations considered by Carlier and Campos Pinto
300 [19] are equivalent to system (1). Also for this work, the authors consider a fully-implicit time discretization,
301 which yields a time-reversible and energy-conserving numerical scheme, and directly approximate the velocity
302 \mathbf{u} instead of the momentum \mathbf{m} . However, they do not discuss asymptotic preservation, nor do they deal with
303 discontinuous flows. Again, we conjecture that switching to conservative variables and adding a nonlinear
304 stabilization, could make the method [19] work also in the case of nonsmooth solutions.

305 4. Computational results

306 In this section we validate the proposed method against some well-known benchmark problems. In
307 particular, the numerical tests can be divided in two categories:

- 308 • In Sections 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.5 we consider inviscid weakly compressible flows with variable density.
309 For these tests, the MOOD limiter described in Section 3.3 is necessary for the stability of the scheme
310 when shocks and nonsmooth solutions are considered. In particular, the physical viscosity is zero, and
311 the viscosities ϵ_ρ , ϵ_S and $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}}$ are purely numerical, and they are computed as explained in Sections 3.3
312 and 3.4.
- 313 • In Sections 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10 we consider viscid incompressible fluids with constant density.
314 For these tests we assume $\rho = 1$ and, since the density remains constant, the MOOD limiter is never
315 activated, so that $\epsilon_\rho = \epsilon_S = 0$, and $\epsilon_{\mathbf{m}} = \nu = \mu$, with μ being the physical viscosity.

The scheme has been implemented in the finite element library `NGSolve` [92]. In the figures, the new
scheme is referred to as “DG-FEEC”, since it is based on both discontinuous Galerkin (DG) methods and
compatible finite element exterior calculus (FEEC). Unless otherwise specified, the time-step is computed
with the CFL condition

$$\Delta t = C_{\text{CFL}} \frac{h}{(2r+1)\sigma},$$

316 with C_{CFL} the Courant number, h being a characteristic mesh size and $\sigma \doteq \max(\|u\|_\infty, 1)$. If not stated
317 otherwise, $C_{\text{CFL}} = 0.25$ and the physical parameters are $\gamma = 1.4$ and $c_v = 2.5$. We say that we employ

318 polynomials of degree r to as a short-hand for the finite element spaces Σ_{r+1} , RT_r and dP_r . If not otherwise
 319 specified, the symmetric positive definite linear systems are solved with the sparse Cholesky factorization
 320 available in `NGSolve` [92]. Finally the parameter ζ in the interior-penalty bilinear form is chosen as $\zeta =$
 321 $5(r+1)^2$, so that some dissipation is present also in the case $r = 0$.

322 4.1. Isentropic vortex

To validate the spatial accuracy of the proposed method in the compressible regime, we consider the
 inviscid isentropic vortex proposed by Hu and Shu [93]. The domain is the square $\Omega = [0, 10]^2$ with periodic
 boundary conditions. The stationary solution is

$$\begin{aligned}\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) &= (1 + \delta T)^{\frac{1}{\gamma-1}}, \\ p(\mathbf{x}, t) &= (1 + \delta T)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}}, \\ \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \frac{5}{2\pi} e^{\frac{1-r^2}{2}} (5 - y, x - 5),\end{aligned}$$

323 with $\delta T(\mathbf{x}, t) = -(\gamma - 1) \frac{25}{8\gamma\pi^2} e^{1-r^2}$ and $r = \sqrt{(x-5)^2 + (y-5)^2}$. We run the simulation until $t_{\text{end}} = 1$ with
 324 a sequence of unstructured meshes M_N with $N = 40, 60, 80, 100, 120$ being the number of intervals on each
 325 side of the square, and we consider polynomial degrees $r = 0, 1, 2$. The resulting errors and convergence rates
 326 are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively. As expected, the convergence rate is $r + 1$ when polynomials of
 degree r are used.

Table 1: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 1$ for the isentropic vortex benchmark in 2D with $\mathbf{m}_h \in \text{RT}_0$.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\rho_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\rho_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M_{40}	$1.1786 \cdot 10^{-1}$		$4.0867 \cdot 10^{-1}$		$1.4399 \cdot 10^{-1}$	
M_{60}	$8.0714 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.93	$2.8752 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.87	$9.8315 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.94
M_{80}	$6.1388 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.95	$2.1672 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.98	$7.4789 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.95
M_{100}	$4.9716 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.95	$1.7598 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.93	$6.0597 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.94
M_{120}	$4.1559 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.98	$1.4757 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.97	$5.0599 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.99

327

Table 2: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 1$ for the isentropic vortex benchmark in 2D with $\mathbf{m}_h \in \text{RT}_1$.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\rho_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\rho_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M_{40}	$3.3423 \cdot 10^{-3}$		$1.0999 \cdot 10^{-2}$		$4.2149 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
M_{60}	$1.4795 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.01	$4.8212 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.03	$1.8802 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.99
M_{80}	$8.6110 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.88	$2.6915 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.03	$1.0898 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.90
M_{100}	$5.4473 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.05	$1.7498 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.93	$6.9309 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.03
M_{120}	$3.5057 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.42	$1.1496 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.30	$4.4690 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.41

328 In order to showcase the superiority of the hybridized method over the non-hybridized one, we repeat
 329 this test considering the same sequence of meshes and polynomials of degree w until $t_{\text{end}} = 0.1$ considering
 330 four different linear solvers for system (24):

- 331 • the hybridized method (27) with the conjugate gradient algorithm (H-CG);
- 332 • the hybridized method (27) with the Cholesky sparse factorization (H-Cholesky);

Figure 1: Pressure at time $t = 1$ for the smooth acoustic wave test.

- 333 • the non-hybridized method (24) with the generalized minimal residual algorithm [94] (NH-GMRES);
- 334 • the non-hybridized method (24) with the sparse direct factorization from PARDISO [95] (NH-PARDISO).

335 For the iterative methods we use the Jacobi preconditioner. We keep track of the average wall-clock time
 336 needed to solve (24). The result are shown in Table 4. As expected, we observe that the hybridized
 337 method clearly outperforms the non-hybridized one, for both direct and iterative solvers.

338 4.2. Smooth acoustic wave

We consider now the propagation of the wave given at time $t = 0$ by

$$p(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 1 + e^{-\alpha r^2}, \quad \rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 1, \quad \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \mathbf{0},$$

339 with $\alpha = 40$ and $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. The domain is the periodic square $\Omega = [-2, 2]^2$, and is discretized with
 340 a 120×120 unstructured triangular mesh. For this test we choose $C_{\text{CFL}} = 0.1$ and we use polynomials of
 341 degree 1. The pressure at the final time $t_{\text{end}} = 1$ is plotted in Figure 1. For this test, we can compute a
 342 reference solution by solving the equations in the radial direction with a second-order explicit finite volume
 343 scheme, see also [29] and [96]. A comparison with the reference solution and the proposed method with
 344 polynomials of degree 1 and a 120×120 mesh is shown in Figure 2. A good agreement is observed between
 345 the proposed methodology and the reference solution.

346 4.3. Circular explosion

To test the robustness of the proposed method on shocks and moderate Mach number flows, we consider
 now a two-dimensional circular explosion problem (see e.g. [97, 98]). The computational domain is the
 square $\Omega = [-1, 1]^2$ with periodic boundary conditions. The initial data are given by

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } r \leq 0.5, \\ 0.125 & \text{if } r > 0.5, \end{cases} \quad p(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } r \leq 0.5, \\ 0.1 & \text{if } r > 0.5, \end{cases} \quad \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \mathbf{0}.$$

347 We run the simulation using polynomials of degree 2 until $t_{\text{end}} = 0.25$ on a 120×120 unstructured mesh. The
 348 density at the final time is shown in Figure 3, together with the troubled elements on which the artificial

Table 3: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 1$ for the isentropic vortex benchmark in 2D with $\mathbf{m}_h \in \text{RT}_2$.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\rho_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\rho_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M_{40}	$1.6147 \cdot 10^{-4}$		$8.2252 \cdot 10^{-4}$		$1.9950 \cdot 10^{-4}$	
M_{60}	$4.5158 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.14	$2.5168 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.92	$5.6302 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.12
M_{80}	$1.8496 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.10	$1.0639 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.99	$2.3203 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.08
M_{100}	$9.4169 \cdot 10^{-6}$	3.03	$5.4099 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.03	$1.1721 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.06
M_{120}	$5.2539 \cdot 10^{-6}$	3.20	$2.9573 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.31	$6.6115 \cdot 10^{-6}$	3.14

Table 4: Average wall-clock time (in seconds) needed to solve linear system (24) with different linear solvers and mesh sizes for the isentropic vortex. We are considering polynomials of degree 2.

Mesh	H-CG	H-Cholesky	NH-GMRES	NH-PARDISO
M_{40}	1.90s	1.81s	13.80s	9.84s
M_{60}	4.68s	4.70s	26.84s	32.55s
M_{80}	7.95s	11.12s	47.18s	107.76s
M_{100}	13.16s	20.58s	84.59s	179.11s
M_{120}	19.53s	43.35s	144.43s	396.38s

Figure 2: Density, pressure and radial velocity along $x = 0$ for the smooth acoustic wave test. Comparison between the DG-FEEC method and the reference solution.

Figure 3: Density at time $t = 0.25$ for the circular explosion problem. The artificial viscosity is applied only on the red elements.

Figure 4: Density, pressure and radial velocity along $x = 0$ for the circular explosion test. Comparison between the reference solution and the new DG-FEEC method with polynomial approximation degree two and *a posteriori* artificial viscosity.

viscosity was applied. As for the smooth acoustic wave test, we have computed a reference solution by solving the equations in the radial direction, see [57]. A comparison between the reference solution and the proposed method is shown in Figure 4.

We observe that the *a posteriori* artificial viscosity is applied only near discontinuities, so that the method does not exhibit spurious oscillations while maintaining the high order accuracy. We remark that for this test the artificial viscosity is necessary: if it is not present, the density becomes negative and the numerical solution blows up before reaching the final time.

4.4. Numerical sensitivity study concerning the choice of the path

In this section we carefully study the sensitivity of the choice of the path for the non-conservative entropy transport equation (1c) in the context of a first order explicit path-conservative DG scheme [68, 69, 70] in 1D, which is fully equivalent to a first order path-conservative Godunov-type finite volume scheme. The cell averages are updated as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q}_i^{n+1} = \mathbf{Q}_i^n - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \left(\mathbf{f}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} - \mathbf{f}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} \right) - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \left(\mathbf{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} + \mathbf{D}_{i-\frac{1}{2}} \right), \quad (33)$$

361 using the Rusanov flux for the conservative part

$$\mathbf{f}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{Q}_i^n) + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{Q}_{i+1}^n)) - \frac{1}{2} s_{\max} (\mathbf{Q}_{i+1}^n - \mathbf{Q}_i^n), \quad (34)$$

362 with $s_{\max} = \max(|\lambda_k(\mathbf{Q}_i^n)|, |\lambda_k(\mathbf{Q}_{i+1}^n)|)$ the maximum signal speed at the cell interface and the discrete
363 non-conservative product for the scalar entropy transport given by $\mathbf{D}_{i+\frac{1}{2}}^S = (0, \mathbf{0}, D_{i+\frac{1}{2}}^S)$ with

$$D_{i+\frac{1}{2}}^S = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} (S_{i+1}^n - S_i^n). \quad (35)$$

364 Here, $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}}$ is the average velocity in the normal direction. In the following we study the sensitivity of the
365 numerical results with respect to the choice of the path. We employ the following different averages of the
366 velocity at the interface $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}}$, which correspond either to different choices of the path and/or to different
367 quadrature rules. For the sake of simplicity we only report the final average of the velocity for six rather
368 different choices:

- 369 1. Path P1 (segment path in primitive variables, exact integral): $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{2} (u_i^n + u_{i+1}^n)$;
- 370 2. Path P2 (segment path in conservative variables, mid-point rule): $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{(\rho u)_i^n + (\rho u)_{i+1}^n}{\rho_i^n + \rho_{i+1}^n}$;
- 371 3. Path P3 (classical Roe average of the velocity [99, 57] for the compressible Euler equations):
372 $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{u_i^n \sqrt{\rho_i^n} + u_{i+1}^n \sqrt{\rho_{i+1}^n}}{\sqrt{\rho_i^n} + \sqrt{\rho_{i+1}^n}}$;
- 373 4. Path P4 (segment path in conservative variables, Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule with $M = 5$ quadra-
374 ture nodes): $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \sum_{j=1}^M \omega_j u(\mathbf{Q}_i^n + \xi_j(\mathbf{Q}_{i+1}^n - \mathbf{Q}_i^n))$;
- 375 5. Path P5 (polynomial path in conservative variables, Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule with $M = 5$
376 quadrature nodes): $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \sum_{j=1}^M \omega_j u(\mathbf{Q}_i^n + \xi_j^5(\mathbf{Q}_{i+1}^n - \mathbf{Q}_i^n))$;
- 377 6. Path P6 (polynomial path in primitive variables, Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule with $M = 5$ quadra-
378 ture nodes): $\tilde{u}_{i+\frac{1}{2}} = \sum_{j=1}^M \omega_j (u_i^n + \xi_j^5(u_{i+1}^n - u_i^n))$.

The 1D computational domain is $\Omega = [-0.5, +0.5]$ and is discretized with 500 elements. The CFL number is set to CFL=0.9 and the final time is $t = 0.2$. The initial condition is given by

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 0.5, \\ 0.125 & \text{if } x > 0, \end{cases} \quad p(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 0, \\ 0.1 & \text{if } x > 0, \end{cases} \quad \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \mathbf{0}.$$

379 The obtained computational results are presented in Figure 5 and are compared with a numerical reference
380 solution obtained by a conservative second order MUSCL-Hancock-type FV scheme [57] solving for ρS
381 instead of S , using a very fine grid of 10000 elements. Indeed, combining the mass conservation equation
382 (1a) with the entropy transport equation (1c) yields the following conservative equation for the entropy
383 density:

$$\partial_t(\rho S) + \nabla \cdot (\rho S \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (36)$$

384 which can be solved by standard methods for systems of hyperbolic conservation laws. As expected, the
385 influence of the choice of the path is only very marginal. For more detailed discussions on path-conservative
386 schemes, see [100, 101, 68].

387 4.5. Kelvin-Helmholtz instability at low Mach

We consider now the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability test on the periodic square $\Omega = [-1, 1]^2$. The initial condition for this test is

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= 1 - \frac{1}{4} \tanh\left(25\left(|y| - \frac{1}{2}\right)\right), & p(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= \frac{10^4}{\gamma}, \\ \mathbf{u}_1(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= -\frac{1}{2} \tanh\left(25\left(|y| - \frac{1}{2}\right)\right), & \mathbf{u}_2(\mathbf{x}, 0) &= \frac{1}{100} \sin(2\pi x) \cos(2\pi y). \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5: Sensitivity study on the choice of the path and comparison with the exact solution of the conservative system based on the entropy density ρS rather than on the specific entropy S .

Figure 6: Density at times $t = 2, 3, 4, 5$ for the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability test.

388 The domain is discretized with a 120×120 unstructured triangular mesh, and for this test we employ
 389 polynomials of degree 1. The density at times $t = 2, 3, 4, 5$ is displayed in Figure 6 for a qualitative
 390 comparison with other references. We remark that this test is outside the theoretical framework of this
 391 work, since it is in the incompressible regime, but the density is not constant.

392 4.6. Taylor-Green vortex at low Mach

393 To verify the expected convergence rate of the algorithm and the asymptotic-preserving property, we
 394 consider the stationary Taylor-Green vortex [102]. The computational domain is the periodic box $\Omega =$
 395 $[0, 2\pi]^2$. The exact solution for this test is

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1, \quad \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{pmatrix} \sin(x) \cos(y) \\ -\cos(x) \sin(y) \end{pmatrix}, \quad p(\mathbf{x}, t) = p_0 + \frac{1}{4} (\cos(2x) + \cos(2y)). \quad (37)$$

396 We run this test until $t_{\text{end}} = 0.2$ on 50×50 for $p_0 \in \{5 \cdot 10^3, 5 \cdot 10^4, \dots, 5 \cdot 10^{12}\}$ to show that $\rho_h \rightarrow 1$ and
 397 $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rightarrow 0$ when the Mach number M approaches zero. From [33, 34, 103, 104, 105, 24] we know that this
 398 convergence is quadratic with respect to M . We verify this property by reporting the L^∞ error of ρ_h and
 399 $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h$ as a function of p_0 and M in Table 5. As expected, second order is reached with respect to M .

Table 5: Spatial L^∞ error norms and convergence rates of $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h$ and ρ_h with respect to the Mach number M at time $t = 0.2$ for the Taylor-Green vortex benchmark in 2D on a 50×50 mesh with polynomials of degree 1.

p_0	M	$L_\Omega^\infty(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h)$	$L_\Omega^\infty(\rho_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
$5 \cdot 10^3$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.4721 \cdot 10^{-5}$		$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-5}$	
$5 \cdot 10^4$	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.4720 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2.00	$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^5$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.4720 \cdot 10^{-7}$	2.00	$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-7}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^6$	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.4720 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.00	$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-8}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^7$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.4719 \cdot 10^{-9}$	2.00	$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-9}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^9$	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.4726 \cdot 10^{-10}$	2.00	$1.0845 \cdot 10^{-10}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^9$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.4810 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.00	$1.0844 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^{10}$	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.4292 \cdot 10^{-12}$	2.01	$1.0894 \cdot 10^{-12}$	2.00
$5 \cdot 10^{11}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.3112 \cdot 10^{-13}$	1.87	$1.0703 \cdot 10^{-13}$	2.02
$5 \cdot 10^{12}$	$3.78 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$2.1806 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.92	$6.6613 \cdot 10^{-15}$	2.41

400 We now run the simulation until $t_{\text{end}} = 0.5$ with the same sequence of meshes used for the isentropic
 401 vortex and $p_0 = 10^7$. We use polynomials of degree r with $r = 0, 1, 2$ and we set $C_{\text{CFL}} = 0.5$. The results are
 402 shown in Tables 6, 7 and 8 respectively. As expected, we observe $r + 1$ -th order accuracy for both velocity
 403 and pressure when using polynomials of degree r .

404 To test the conservation properties of our scheme, we now repeat the test with $p_0 = 1e - 7$ until
 405 $t_{\text{end}} = 10$ using the coarser mesh, $r = 2$, keeping track of total energy $E = \frac{1}{2} \int_\Omega \rho |\mathbf{u}|^2 dx$, total momentum
 406 $m_i = \int_\Omega m_i dx$ for $i = 1, 2$ and incompressibility $\|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}\|$. The evolution of these quantities is displayed in
 407 Figure 7. For the energy, we observe a remarkably slow dissipation rate (less than $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ per time unit),
 408 while momentum and incompressibility have an error of the same order of magnitude of the square of the
 409 Mach number.

410 4.7. Double Shear Layer at low Mach

We consider now the double shear layer test [106]. For this test the computational domain is $\Omega = [-1, 1]^2$ with periodic boundary conditions. The viscosity is set to $\mu = 2 \times 10^{-4}$. We consider an initial condition

Table 6: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 0.5$ for the Taylor-Green vortex benchmark in 2D with polynomials of degree 0.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M ₄₀	$3.6930 \cdot 10^{-1}$		$2.2559 \cdot 10^{-1}$	
M ₆₀	$2.4669 \cdot 10^{-1}$	1.00	$1.5437 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.94
M ₈₀	$1.8692 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.96	$1.1682 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.97
M ₁₀₀	$1.5159 \cdot 10^{-1}$	0.94	$9.2404 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1.05
M ₁₂₀	$1.2639 \cdot 10^{-1}$	1.00	$7.8722 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.88

Table 7: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 0.5$ for the Taylor-Green vortex benchmark in 2D with polynomials of degree 1.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M ₄₀	$7.2829 \cdot 10^{-3}$		$5.2217 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
M ₆₀	$3.2420 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.00	$2.2959 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.03
M ₈₀	$1.8173 \cdot 10^{-3}$	2.01	$1.3107 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.95
M ₁₀₀	$1.1786 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.94	$8.4328 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.98
M ₁₂₀	$8.2138 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.98	$5.7835 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.07

Table 8: Spatial L^2 error norms and convergence rates at time $t = 0.5$ for the Taylor-Green vortex benchmark in 2D with polynomials of degree 2.

Mesh	$L^2_{\Omega}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{u}_h)$	$L^2_{\Omega}(p_h)$	$\mathcal{O}(p_h)$
M ₄₀	$2.0769 \cdot 10^{-4}$		$9.2427 \cdot 10^{-5}$	
M ₆₀	$6.1905 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.99	$2.6740 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.06
M ₈₀	$2.6161 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.99	$1.1173 \cdot 10^{-5}$	3.03
M ₁₀₀	$1.3545 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.95	$5.8688 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2.89
M ₁₂₀	$7.8322 \cdot 10^{-6}$	3.00	$3.4815 \cdot 10^{-6}$	2.86

Figure 7: Evolution of energy (left), momentum (center), incompressibility (right) for the inviscid Taylor-Green vortex for the time interval $t \in [0, 10]$. For this test we have used a 40×40 mesh and polynomials of degree 2.

Figure 8: Vorticity at times $t = 0.8, 1.6, 2.4$ and 3.6 for the Double Shear Layer test.

given by

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1, \quad p(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \frac{10^4}{\gamma}, \quad \mathbf{u}_1(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} \tanh[\hat{\rho}(\hat{y} - 0.25)] & \text{if } \hat{y} \leq 0.5, \\ \tanh[\hat{\rho}(0.75 - \hat{y})] & \text{if } \hat{y} > 0.5, \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_2(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \delta \sin(2\pi\hat{x}), \quad \hat{x} = \frac{x+1}{2}, \quad \hat{y} = \frac{y+1}{2},$$

411 with $\hat{\rho} = 30$ and $\delta = 0.05$ being the parameters that determine the slope of the shear layer and the amplitude
 412 of the initial perturbation. For this test we use a mesh with 120 elements on each side and we use a fixed
 413 time-step $\Delta t = 10^{-4}$. The contours of the vorticity ω_h at times $t = 0.8, 1.6, 2.4$ and 3.6 are shown in
 414 Figure 8 for a qualitative comparison with other references, see e.g. [106, 107, 96, 108, 109].

415 4.8. Lid-driven cavity at low Mach

416 We consider the classical lid-driven cavity problem proposed by Ghia, Ghia and Shin [110]. The domain
 417 is $\Omega = [-0.5, 0.5]^2$ with Dirichlet boundary conditions for the velocity. In particular, we set $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (1, 0)$ if
 418 $y = 0.5$ and $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (0, 0)$ otherwise. For this test, we set $\mu = 0.01$. We discretize the domain with a mesh that
 419 has 40 elements on each side and we run the simulation until $t_{\text{end}} = 10$. The result is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Contour plot of \mathbf{u}_1 (left) for the lid-driven cavity test with $\mu = 0.01$ and comparison with the reference solution of [110] for $\mathbf{u}_1(0, y)$ and $\mathbf{u}_2(x, 0)$ (right).

420 An excellent agreement with the reference solution from [110] is observed. We repeat now the same test
 421 with $\mu = 0.001$ and the same mesh, but this time we run the simulation until a steady state is reached.
 422 The result is shown in Figure 10. Again, good agreement is observed between our method and the reference
 423 solution from [110].

424 4.9. Backward-facing step at low Mach

We consider now the backward-facing step problem originally investigated experimentally by Armaly et al. [111]. From the numerical point of view, we follow the set up reported by Lucca et al. [112]. In particular, the computational domain is $\Omega = [-L, 0] \times [0, h] \cup [0, 29.1] \times [-0.097, h]$ with $L = 1.94$ and $h = 0.103$. At the inlet we impose the Poiseuille velocity $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (\bar{u}_1, 0)$ with

$$\bar{u}_1(x, y) = \frac{\Delta p}{2L\mu}y(h - y),$$

where $\Delta p = -3.060845359$. At the outlet we impose a constant pressure, while at all the other boundaries we impose no-slip wall boundary conditions. For this test, the Reynolds number Re is defined as

$$\text{Re} \doteq \frac{2hU}{\nu},$$

with U being the average inlet velocity, i.e.

$$U \doteq \frac{1}{h} \int_0^h \bar{u}_1 dy.$$

425 We run the simulation until $t_{\text{end}} = 80.0$ for $\text{Re} = 44, 100, 200, 300, 400$. For this test, we set $C_{\text{CFL}} = 0.1$.
 426 The results obtained with $r = 2$ and $h_{\text{max}} = 0.04$ are shown in Figure 11, in which we perform a qualitative
 427 comparison with the experimental results obtained by Armaly et al. [111] and the numerical ones computed
 428 by Tavelli and Dumbser [81] and by Lucca et al. [112].

429 4.10. Viscous flow around a cylinder at low Mach

430 We consider now the case of a viscous flow around a cylinder [113, 114, 112]. The computational domain
 431 is a rectangle with vertices $(0, 0)$, $(50, 0)$, $(50, 20)$, $(0, 20)$ minus a circle centered in $(10, 10)$ with radius
 432 0.5. The domain is discretized with a mesh made by 9168 elements with \mathcal{P}_3 curved boundaries around the
 433 cylinder. The following boundary conditions are imposed:

Figure 10: Contour plot of u_1 (left) for the lid-driven cavity test with $\mu = 0.001$ and comparison with the reference solution of [110] for $u_1(0, y)$ and $u_2(x, 0)$ (right).

Figure 11: Streamlines and horizontal component of the velocity around the step for the backward-facing step test for $Re = 400$ (left) and normalized recirculation point versus Reynolds number, compared with the experimental results from [111] and the numerical ones from [81, 112] (right).

Figure 12: Strouhal number as a function of the Reynolds number.

Figure 13: Detail of the vorticity around the cylinder for $Re = 185$ at $t = 100$.

- 434 • Inflow with $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (1, 0)$ at the left boundary;
- 435 • Outflow with $\bar{p} = 0$ at all the other boundaries of the rectangle;
- 436 • No-slip wall on the boundary of the cylinder.

437 We compute the shedding frequency f of the vorticity evaluated at the point $P = (15, 10)$. In Figure 12 we
 438 plot the computed Strouhal number St (which for this test coincides with f) as a function of the Reynolds
 439 number $Re = 1/\mu$. We compare our results with those obtained using the semi-implicit DG scheme proposed
 440 by Tavelli and Dumbser [81], the experimental data of Williamson and Brown [113] and the so-called universal
 441 Strouhal curve. We remark that for this test we are using less elements than [81] and [112], but the computed
 442 solution still agrees well with the reference solutions. The vorticity at time $t = 100$ with $Re = 185$ is shown
 443 in Figure 13.

444 5. Conclusions

445 In this paper, we have introduced a novel semi-implicit method for weakly compressible flows based on
 446 compatible finite elements. This method achieves arbitrary high order in space and ensures exact mass con-

447 servation at the discrete level. Our proposed semi-implicit scheme leverages an operator splitting technique,
 448 as discussed in previous works [21, 80, 24, 115, 25]. The nonlinear convective terms are discretized using an
 449 explicit discontinuous Galerkin method, while all other terms are handled implicitly. Notably, each iteration
 450 involves solving only symmetric positive definite linear systems, thanks to the hybridization technique.
 451 When the Mach number approaches zero and density remains constant, our method tends to an exactly
 452 divergence-free scheme for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. The asymptotic-preserving property
 453 has also been verified numerically, where we find quadratic convergence of the density and the divergence
 454 errors in terms of the Mach number, as expected. Additionally, we have incorporated an *a posteriori* limiter
 455 via artificial viscosity based on the MOOD approach. Finally, we validated the new scheme against a set of
 456 classical benchmark problems for both compressible and incompressible flows.

457 Due to the employed splitting approach, the numerical schemes proposed in this paper are so far limited
 458 to first order of accuracy in time. However, higher order time accuracy can be easily achieved, for example,
 459 at the aid of IMEX Runge-Kutta time integrators, see e.g. [47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52].

460 Looking ahead, we plan to extend our scheme to viscous compressible flows by incorporating a discretiza-
 461 tion of the full Navier-Stokes tensor via the MCS method (e.g., [116, 117]). Additionally, we aim to design
 462 a scheme capable of solving all Mach number flows, similar to the approaches in [118, 29, 52]. Another
 463 promising direction is extending our method to magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) by adding a conforming
 464 discretization of the magnetic field, as demonstrated in works such as [119, 120, 121].

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